

REGULATORY FRAMEWORK ISSUED IN UZBEKISTAN TO ENSURE THE INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRODUCTION

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Abstract. There are a number of regulatory legal acts on the development of science, support of innovative activities, strengthening the legal base of the industry and ensuring the integration of Science, Education and production

Keywords. Regulatory legal acts, science, integration, innovation ideas

Introduction. In the conditions of today's globalization, rapid progress of Science and technology, ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy through the training of highly qualified specialists with deep modern knowledge, achieving a wide introduction of innovative scientific developments into production puts new high demands on science, education and business.[1] The acceleration of innovation processes largely depends on state support. The experience of developed foreign countries shows that the country's economy will be reformed, structurally transformed, the national economy will increase competitiveness, the rapid development of production based directly on high technologies, innovation technologies will be provided to the economy. This entails the development of Science, the support of innovative activities, the strengthening of the legal base of the industry. In our country, a number of regulatory legal acts have been created on ensuring the integration of Science, Education and production, and let us dwell on their brief content below.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS BA METHODOLOGY. At the time of writing this article, The Republic of Uzbekistan relied on the legal framework of the field of development of science, support of innovative activities. On the basis of a systematic, chronological methodology, the processes of production integration of the field of science were studied from the legal side.

Results. Today, science and education are becoming the productive force of society in an increasingly powerful way.[3]. Science and education is a socio-economic and political resource of the power of any state. The pace of economic

growth is now determined not only by the knowledge of physical capital or human qualifications, but also by the ability to apply knowledge to production.[4].

Discussion. PQ-916 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 15, 2008“on additional measures to promote the implementation of innovative projects and technologies in production” in order to create practical mechanisms for the development of scientific and practical research and innovation developments and to promote the modernization of production, application to technical and technological renewal processes, to ensure a more, taking into account the importance of the Republican Fair of innovative ideas and projects in establishing continuous cooperation between research organizations and enterprises of real economy sectors, it was established that the Republican Fair of innovative ideas, technologies and projects will be held annually.[2] Also in this decision, Ministries, Departments, associations to ensure that practical scientific developments and innovative technologies are widely applied to production, companies and other economic associations are tasked with providing assistance to economic management bodies and enterprises in the creation of structural units responsible for the development of network and Enterprise Innovation, and, if necessary, project and design bureaus. In order to further increase the importance of academic science in the development of innovation of the economy, improve the prestige and functioning of the Academy of Sciences, form a unified system of management and regulation of research and innovation activities, as well as increase the place of Science in the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 17, 2017, on measures to further improve management and financing, Resolution No. 2789 of PQ-2789, which is defined as the main tasks and areas of activity of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan:[2]

- conduct fundamental, applied and innovative scientific research in the field of natural, technical and social-humanitarian Sciences; .[5]
- strengthening and development of mechanisms of integration of Science with education and production;
- developing proposals for the development of Science and technology, the formation of priorities of State Scientific and technical programs, being able to calculate the needs of the sectors of the economy and the regions of the Republic;
- study and analyze the achievements of world and Republic science, develop recommendations on their use in the interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- popularization and promotion of the achievements of science, scientific potential, Science and technology of our country;
- international cooperation with Academies of Sciences, Research Organizations and foundations of foreign countries, participation in the organization and holding of international scientific forums and conferences; [6]

-participation in the training of highly qualified personnel, using the scientific potential and material and technical base of the institutions of the Academy of Sciences.[7].

The first paragraph of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 08.10.2019 "on approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" provides for the establishment of mutually beneficial cooperation of education with production enterprises and research institutes"[8]. In the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No 27.07.2017 PQ-3151 "on measures to further expand the participation of sectors and sectors of the economy in improving the quality of training of specialists with higher education"....[9] January 2017 by a prestigious group of foreign experts engaged in the cooperation of the United Nations Committee on Educational, Scientific and Cultural Affairs (UNESCO) and the consulting organization (DGP Research & Consulting - based on the results of the analysis of the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in June, the results of the analysis on complex learning show that the integrity of theory and practice is not ensured in the process of Higher Education, the transfer of student qualification practices at production enterprises is not effectively organized, [10] so that the majority of graduates, instead of, lack of qualified pedagogical and managerial personnel in educational institutions, insufficient effective cooperation with foreign educational institutions..."were noted as flaws.[11] At the same time, in order to ensure the quality of education in higher education institutions for the implementation of the law, the following points are mentioned in Annex 2, Paragraph 4 of the legislative plan (roadmap) of the actions carried out during the academe [12] mic year: "...Formation of orders for the training of Higher Education personnel of ministries and departments within the complexes of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to approve a program of measures to radically improve the level and quality of training of specialists in higher educational institutions and to conduct student practices in enterprises and organizations of the system, to carry out scientific work in cooperation, to ensure the employment of graduates of higher educational institutions.[13].

Conclusion. In a word, this decision can be said to be an important program that determines the further development of the field of Science in our country and the prospects for the integration of Science, Education and production in our Republic.

REFERENCES

1.Ш. М. Мирзиёев –Тошкент : Ўзбекистон. Миллий тараққиёт йўлимизни қатъият билан давом эттириб, янги босқичга кўтарамиз

2.ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИНИ 2030 ЙИЛГАЧА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ КОНЦЕПЦИЯСИНИ ТАСДИҚЛАШ ТЎҒРИСИДА. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Фармони, 08.10.2019 йилдаги ПФ-5847-сон. <https://lex.uz/docs/4545884>.

3. MAHAMMADOVNA S. I. Taъlim жараёнини мониторинг тадқиқ қилиш учун таъхис материалларини ишлаб чиқиш //Results of National Scientific Research. – 2022.

4. Mahammadovna S. I. Needs and Factors for Developing Professional and Creative Abilities of Students of Higher Educational Institutions //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – Т. 25. – №. 6. – С. 2804-2810.

5. Mahammadovna S. I. IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE ENGINEERS BASED ON THE CLUSTER APPROACH //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 3. – С. 45-47.

6. Sirojiddinova I. M. ENGINEERING STUDENTS HAVE SUCCEEDED IN CREATING A TECHNOLOGY CLUSTER // Pedagogy & Psychology Theory and practice International scientific journal № 5 (43), 2022 ISSN 2412-8201. Volgograd, 2022/ 22-25 <http://scippjournal.ru/archives/22-25/12>.

7. Khamidovna P. O. Issues of development of the communication culture of technical students //world of science: journal on modern research methodologies. – 2023. – т. 2. – №. 3. – с. 32-35.

8. Khamidovna P. O. On the Issues of Studying the Problems of Unorganized Youth //Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 316-318.

9. Khamidovna P. O. Features of the Use of Modern Didactic Tools in Technical Higher Educational Institutions //Telematique. – 2023. – С. 7630–7634-7630–7634.

10. PO Khamidovna. [COMMUNICATION CULTURE OF INDIVIDUALS](#) // European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements // EJHEA – 2023.- Т.4.- №4 С-32-36

11. Pulatova O. ISSUES OF ORGANIZING INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS //International Conference on Education and Social Science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 164-168.

12. Пулатова О. Х. ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ КАСБИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ ХОРИЖИЙ ТАЖРИБАЛАР ОРҚАЛИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ //MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND INNOVATIVE TEACHING SOLUTIONS. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 53-62.

13. Пулатова О. Х. ТАЛАБА ШАХСНИНГ КАМОЛ ТОПИШИДА ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТНИНГ ЎРНИ //MODERN PROBLEMS IN EDUCATION AND THEIR SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 6-14.